

WAYS TO OPTIMIZE CULTURE AND ART MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6549851>

Oblanazarova Adiba Alisher qizi

Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

“Library and Information Activity”

Third year student of education

Abstract: *This article is written about new trends and advantages of modern management and marketing development in the field of culture and arts.*

Keywords: *Conceptual skills, theater, cinema, fine and applied arts, management, potential, consulting, information, interpersonal, marketing, financial literacy.*

As in any field today, it is important to use new approaches and new methods of work in the planning and management of cultural and artistic institutions. As our society moves to a market economy, adherence to modern management and marketing rules can be effective in the management of culture and the arts.

The subject of art management is the study of the forms, models and methods of organization that exist in different historical periods and social systems in an entire field of art and its specific areas (theater, cinema, fine and applied arts). It is said. The main goal of art management is to carry out appropriate organizational work that helps to increase the value and social status of art activities in a market economy.

The goals and objectives of art management include:

- Creation of a system (model) of cultural life based on administrative and cultural policy;
- planning of cultural development;
- creation of network systems in the field of art;
- constant monitoring of the effectiveness of organizations in the field of art;
- staff incentives;
- search and acquisition of new art markets;
- Development of forms and models of international cooperation in the field of art.

As an integral part of modern management, art management has the following tasks:

- Defining the goals of the development of the arts organization;
- development of its strategy;
- Development of a system of measures to solve problems;
- control over the implementation of tasks.

It is advisable to divide the field of art management into commercial and non-commercial. The commercial sector includes mainly small and medium-sized businesses in the field of art. For example, private galleries, pottery workshops, workshops for repair and restoration of works of fine art, design and advertising agencies, art salons and shops, art auctions, special training courses on art programs such as commercial organizations. Non-profit organizations include art secondary and higher education institutions, museums, symphony orchestras, theaters, and more. Management aims to make a profit in commercial organizations and to meet certain socio-cultural needs in non-profit organizations. This is the nature of art management. Depending on the purpose, the activities of art managers are also different.

The manager's responsibility is to ensure the efficient and rational use of resources to achieve the organization's goals. It is impossible to look at the work of a manager one-sidedly. It requires a wide range of knowledge and skills. Some researchers have developed long lists of knowledge and skills that a leader should have. According to Richard L. Daft, they can be divided into three categories: conceptual, human, and technical skills. Their level of need varies depending on the manager's position.

Conceptual skills are the cognitive abilities of a person to understand the organization as a whole, as well as to clearly distinguish the interrelationships of organizational units. These skills include the manager's thinking, the ability to process the information received, and the ability to plan. The manager should have an idea of the role of each department of the institution, its position in the network and in the wider business and social environment. This requires the person to have strategic thinking skills.

Conceptual skills are needed by managers at all levels, but they are especially important for senior managers. It is imperative that these managers understand the nature of each situation that arises, identify the key factors, and anticipate the future course of events.

Human skills are the ability of a manager to work with people. The manager's human skills are reflected in the motivation of subordinates to

prove themselves and their involvement in the activities of the organization. Such a manager can communicate well with other people.

The growing importance of human skills is driven by the rapid pace of globalization, the growing diversity of the workforce, and the increasing competition for highly skilled professionals. Modern managers need to consider not only the material needs of employees, but also their emotional needs. Today, employees expect the manager to provide leadership, respect, and the opportunity to contribute to the organization as much as possible. Human skills are becoming increasingly important for managers at all levels, especially those who interact directly with employees on a daily basis.

Technical skills are specialized knowledge and skills used to perform work tasks, i.e., the ability to apply the techniques, technology, and equipment needed to perform certain functions, such as research, production, or finance. A manager's technical skills indicate that he or she has professional knowledge and analytical skills in a particular field. Technical skills are at the heart of lower management. Many employees have reached their first management positions through their technical skills. But as you move up to the next level, the need for technical skills will diminish, and the importance of human and conceptual skills will increase.

The conceptual, human and technical skills of managers help them to perform key management functions in large and small, production and service, commercial and non-profit organizations. The responsibilities of a manager are varied. A number of studies have been conducted to describe them, with Henry Mintzberg providing the best answers to questions about the manager's day-to-day operations. The researcher followed the managers involved in the study for months at a time, keeping track of what they were doing. G. Mintzberg singled out three descriptions of management activities and ten roles performed by managers. Subsequent studies have confirmed the researcher's conclusions.

Research by G. Mintzberg and other scholars has shown that management activities are described by managers in terms of the implementation of ten key roles. A role is a set of perceptions of a manager's behavior. The main roles can be grouped into three conceptual categories:

- 1) Information (information management);
- 2) Interpersonal (human management);
- 3) Decision making (action management).

Each role involves the performance of a specific type of activity, which in turn ensures the performance of the four basic management functions. Information roles are specific to the types of management activities aimed at creating and developing an information network. The general manager spends 75% of his working time talking to other people. The role of the observer means that the manager receives current information from various sources: the manager, colleagues and employees, the media, the subjects of the external environment. Many marketing managers spend more than 50% of their time interacting with customers. The role of distributor and speaker is a reflection of the role of observer, as the manager conveys current information to people inside and outside the organization as they perform.

Interpersonal roles. The fulfillment of such roles by managers requires an emphasis on interaction with other people and the use of human skills. The role of the manager is understood by the manager to conduct ceremonial and symbolic events, to receive guests, to sign legal documents. In a particular position, the manager represents an entire firm. For example, managers reward their best employees. The role of leader requires the manager to act to motivate employees, communicate, and make an impact. As a link, the manager ensures the stability of information communication in both the internal and external environment of the organization.

Decision-making roles come to the forefront when a manager needs to make a choice or act, and it usually requires conceptual and human skills. The role of the entrepreneur is to initiate change. Managers are always thinking about turning the future into the present. Striving to solve current problems will inspire them to take action. The role of the "firefighter" is reflected in actions such as resolving disputes and other problems, resolving conflicts between employees, and adapting to sudden changes in the external environment. The role of resource allocation is related to the decision to use labor, time, and financial resources in the most appropriate and appropriate manner. The manager has to decide which project to invest in or which customer complaints to consider first. The role of the negotiator is to communicate and negotiate, which helps the manager achieve the desired results.

How a manager performs these 10 roles depends on a number of factors, some of which include the role of the manager in the organizational hierarchy, his or her natural intelligence, the type of organization, the goals set, the leader and the link. shows how important

their roles are in managers at different levels. As the manager's position in the organization increases, the role of the leader decreases and the role of the link becomes more important.

The importance of this or that role can be determined by other factors at the same time. To know which role is important at a given time, managers need to constantly monitor what is happening inside and outside the organization. The roles suggested by G. Minsberg can also be applied to art managers. In nonprofits, managers should focus primarily on the roles of speaker, leader, and resource allocator.

The main difference between the activities of commercial and non-commercial managers is that the actions of commercial managers are aimed at making a profit for the firm, that is, to make money, and in non-profit to meet certain social and cultural needs. This difference defines the unique characteristics and requirements of nonprofits. As a result, their managers have to deal with non-commercial issues.

Typically, the source of a nonprofit's financial resources is not the sale of goods and services, but government-sponsored funds, grants, and voluntary donations. But this resource is strictly limited, and managers focus on minimizing costs. If a manager fails to show that he or she can use the money effectively, a new donation or government funding will inevitably be a problem for the organization.

The role of the speaker helps to attract the attention of sponsors and the public. In the context of limited financial resources, motivating employees in arts organizations requires a leadership role from managers. The basis of their work is that non-profit art managers seek new sources of funding to effectively run the organization (museum, theater, symphony orchestra, etc.) and allocate limited funds wisely. Therefore, they need to pay more attention to the role of resource allocators.

In the commercial sector, art organizations are mostly small businesses. In such companies, the role of the speaker comes first, because here every manager has to take the lesser-known, but developing company to the outside world. The role of the entrepreneur does not lose its importance: the manager is required to take a creative approach to their work, to implement new ideas that will help to increase competitiveness.

The creative process and the production of cultural treasures and the creation of conditions for their perception by society are the basis of the activities of the art manager. The activities of the Art Manager include:

- Entrepreneurial manager who organizes the creative process (giving ideas, writing scripts, etc.);

- Manager-organizer of the creation of works of art;
- Sales Manager (exhibitions, tours, books, CD sales), organizing the distribution of cultural products and providing intermediary services
- Marketing manager (information, advertising), who organizes the promotion of culture and art, promotes the acceptance of the cultural process by society;
- Manager of the program for the restoration, preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage.

Today, the manager provides information and communication movement in a horizontal direction, rather than in the traditional vertical connection. This, in turn, accelerates the organization's response to changes in the external environment.

Project managers, functional and general managers working in the horizontal direction of the hierarchy are becoming a requirement of modern business.

Today, with the rapid development of new information technologies, the emergence of electronic forms of business has not bypassed the field of art. The management of e-commerce and Internet organizations, which carry out activities such as the auction of many works of fine and applied arts through the Internet, Internet projects in the field of music, book sales, requires new powers for managers. One of the most important skills a modern manager should have is effective communication, retaining and motivating talented employees. In general, these features have been important to the manager, but their importance is growing in the context of the remote location of employees and the virtual nature of work, for example, in the current coronavirus pandemic. The best managers of today are giving up command and control based on it in order to manage uncertainty and create relationship-oriented, fast-moving, flexible and adaptable organizations.

Leadership is distributed throughout the organization, with managers giving additional powers to employees to stimulate their creativity and generate new ideas. New leadership is based on training, support and guidance. Success in the new environment depends on the strength and quality of the relationship and cooperation. There is a need to develop partnerships not only within the organization, but also outside it - with customers, suppliers and even competitors. The concept of cooperation, on the other hand, knows neither functional, nor hierarchical, nor organizational boundaries. E-business models require managers to

evaluate and manage relationships that do not exist in traditional organizations.

Controlling emergencies has always been part of managerial work. But as our world becomes more dynamic, interconnected, and complex, the frequent occurrence of accidents and, in many cases, the dire consequences, require new competencies and skills from managers. Another important one is to be able to manage crisis situations. Crisis management requires the following skills from the manager:

1. Be able to stay calm.
2. Being in the public eye.
3. Prefer people to business.
4. Be able to tell the truth.
5. Return to previous business.

Being able to stay calm. The leader's emotions are passed on to the staff, so he should be able to look to the future with confidence and remain calm. In a crisis, the manager's job is to calm other people down and eliminate their fears and anxieties. A leader must be able to overcome his fears, hesitations and pains, understand the dangers of the situation, and be strong-willed, hopeful and inspiring to others.

Being able to be in the public eye, a person who feels fear in the face of uncertainty likes the idea that the situation is under someone's control. Being able to be in the public eye in a crisis gives a manager peace of mind, hope and confidence.

Therefore, the manager of culture and the arts is changing today, as he is in other areas of business. This requires a modern manager to be constantly researching and studying.

Marketing (visual market - market, movement in the market, activity) - a form of organization and management of production, services and sales of goods by an enterprise or organization. McCovern coined the term marketing in the 1960s. Marketing was first used in the United States in the early 20th century as a theoretical concept and a unique phenomenon in business.

Marketing is a multifaceted process. Marketing is a process that encourages the development and implementation of a marketing concept, the exchange of ideas, pricing of goods and services, marketing (movement), sales and meeting the goals of individuals and organizations, human is a type of human activity that meets their needs through exchange.

At the same time, it is safe to say that marketing is the business philosophy, thinking strategy and tactics of the subjects of market relations. So marketing is a process of both observation and action. In today's market economy, the principles of marketing are evident in processes ranging from the production of simple goods or services to complex technologies. Today, marketing is used in all kinds of activities related to customer satisfaction.

If marketing is used at the enterprise level, it is called micromarketing. When used nationally or internationally, it is called macromarketing.

Personal marketing is the process of supporting and changing public opinion about a particular person. Many people, especially politicians, artists, doctors, athletes, and businessmen, use personal marketing to spread their fame and grow their business.

Location marketing refers to the activity of changing, organizing, and maintaining customer attitudes toward a particular area or location. For example, in order to increase the number of foreign tourists visiting the ancient cities of Samarkand, Khiva and Bukhara, tourism organizations conduct marketing activities.

The provision of cultural and art services to the population, ie cultural marketing, is one of the areas that need to be developed and improved today. The purpose of covering this topic is to find out how art and cultural institutions provide cultural services to the population, what are the main aspects of cultural marketing and what needs to be done to improve this activity. To do this, we must first answer the question of what is meant by cultural marketing, which has a scientific and methodological significance for our industry, and who are the subjects of its implementation.

Cultural scholars understand cultural services as the organizational and pedagogical work of cultural workers. The associations they organize and the events they hold are interpreted as ordinary performers or spectators of these events. The most important feature of cultural services is the provision of services through orders that express the specific needs and interests of the people. In modern language, we call this cultural marketing.

It is known that for many years the main task of culture and art has been to organize events. Although meeting the needs of the population was stated as their main task, in practice it was almost not followed. Unfortunately, despite so many opportunities, this is still the case in some areas of the arts and culture. For example, cultural centers, parks and recreation centers in many districts of the country are frozen. In the context of rapidly evolving market relations, there is no initiative to promote the development of the industry. The emergence of different cultural centers

requires the expansion of paid services, so that each event is organized in accordance with the specific needs and interests of the people. Here, cultural services are seen as a marketing tool.

A study of the activities of cultural institutions in the United States, the United Kingdom, and Germany shows that they are built on marketing laws and management practices. The key to marketing is not just about performance, but about meeting people's specific needs for a product or service. All the activities of cultural and art institutions are aimed at meeting these needs. Therefore, in these countries, along with the marketing of industries, there is also the marketing of cultural services.

Marketing is being introduced in neighboring republics as a "special philosophy of the organization of the activities of the institution", which opens a wide range of cultural services. Similar changes are taking place in our republic. So, cultural service is an activity that is aimed at meeting the specific needs of people and managing their lives based on these needs.

In practice, there are socio-creative and personal orders of the founders. Socio-creative orders are given by the state, trade unions and other organizations, and individual orders are given by certain groups of citizens. Services spent on orders are valued in the form of salaries or service fees paid by citizens. Cultural services may also be free. Now it is up to cultural institutions to decide which of the events are paid and which are free. Although the marketing approach is based on market relations, it does not rule out free cultural services.

Based on socio-creative orders, cultural services are often considered free. If we remember that the costs of cultural centers (funds for social and creative orders) are separated from various taxes, we realize that the services of cultural institutions have never been free.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Abu Nasr Faroobi. A city of noble people. - Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2016.
2. Avloniy A. Turkish Gulistan or morality. Tashkent: 1993.
3. Asaul A. N. Cultural organizations. Problems of formation and management / M. : Izd-vo «Gumanistka». 2006. 201 p.
4. Abdurahmonov Q.H., Kholmominov Sh.R., Zokirova N.Q. Personnel management. Textbook. - "Teacher", 2008. - 655 p.

5. Bekmurodov M. Organizational culture and leadership spirituality. - Tashkent: 2001.
6. Bekmurodov M.B. Sociology of modern management. - Tashkent: Academy 2019.
7. Bekmurodov B, Kuronbaev Q, Tangriev L. Rapid development and renewal on the basis of action strategy. - Tashkent: Gafur Gulom Publishing House. 2017.
8. Borhard P., Flodel Sh., Mil'ts M., Reinhardt K., Reiter G. The concept of marketing for public libraries. - M.: 1993.
9. Gulyamov S.S. Fundamentals of management. - Tashkent: 2002.
10. Yuldashev N, Kozakov.O. Management. Textbook. - Tashkent: Fan, 2004.